

Feedback to the European Commission call for evidence on 'Virtual worlds (metaverses) – a vision for openness, safety and respect'

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Trilateral Research Ltd welcomes the opportunity to respond to this call for evidence on virtual worlds and metaverses. [Trilateral Research Ltd](#) is an SME that specialises in ethical Artificial Intelligence (AI). With award-winning services in research, data protection and cyber-risk, ethics innovation, and sociotech insights, the team takes an end-to-end approach that fully integrates the technical, legal and social science dimensions of technological research and innovation. This response to the European Commission's call for evidence on virtual worlds and metaverses has been put together by members of Trilateral's Research & Innovation team. The views expressed in this letter belong to the authors only. Our response builds on key results and insights from relevant Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects related to virtual worlds, metaverses, and extended reality (XR) technologies that Trilateral has coordinated and/or collaborated in.

This response to the call for evidence is structured around the objectives as set out by the European Commission for this communication: a vision for open, safe and secure, and respectful virtual worlds.

Open virtual worlds

The current stage of creating virtual worlds reflects the dominance of and massive investments from big global tech companies. The vast nature and the major investment-based development capacity of these players positions them as gatekeepers of the emerging tech field of creating virtual worlds (metaverses).¹ Their rapid progress in building virtual worlds, amidst limited regulatory or monitoring checks, greatly balances the playing field in their favour. This resulting imbalance creates entry barriers for other players (e.g., small and medium enterprises (SMEs)), and unchecked dominance of a market that is still in its early stages. This can negatively affect the freedom, openness, and interoperability of virtual worlds² and stagnate innovation, desired competitiveness, the protection of user rights, and the overall quality of these digital ecosystems.

Trilateral Research, through its work on Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, has interacted with elements related to the provision of open and accessible digital ecosystems. In its ongoing Horizon Europe project [MEMENTOES](#)³ (focusing on building learning-based video games based on historically significant events), preliminary research and project strategy indicate worrying signs of uncertainty towards extended reality (XR) consoles that can be used for immersive experiences (e.g., virtual reality (VR) glasses that can be used for virtual worlds). The current major drawbacks that halt competitive engagement in creating XR digital content include: (a) overall dependency on the major tech corporations; (b) uncertainty of when the next XR device will be

¹ Mohammed, Aliyah. (2022, October 11). *Who controls the metaverse? spoiler alert: It's not policymakers*. VentureBeat. Retrieved April 19, 2023, from <https://venturebeat.com/virtual/who-controls-the-metaverse-spoiler-alert-its-not-policymakers/>.

² Koosha, Ash. (2022, November 10). *The future of the metaverse hinges on interoperability*. Retrieved April 19, 2023, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/90794333/the-future-of-the-metaverse-hinges-on-interoperability>.

³ Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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released and how it will function (both in terms of use and content creation); (c) high cost of XR devices; (d) the sustainability problem of quick turnaround of expensive and tech-heavy XR devices and their short period of relevant use; and (e) lack of easy and simplified interoperability of content between different virtual worlds.

Bearing in mind these practical challenges, SMEs and independent creators are at a great disadvantage in their efforts to create and develop virtual worlds. To promote greater competitiveness, more effort should be dedicated to creating open virtual worlds that enable a diverse range of players to participate in the market and offer their products and services without creating unfair barriers to entry. This can in turn lead to new and innovative solutions that cater to varied interests and needs. To realise and maintain open virtual worlds, efforts should be placed on providing greater interoperability of these systems.⁴ Openness can also promote greater transparency and accountability in the technology, particularly by disclosing how decisions are made and how personal data is collected, stored, used, and protected. These actions can help build public trust and enable informed decision-making on how technology is developed and used in a way that benefits society as a whole. They will also promote respect for human rights, with a focus on the right to privacy, and prevent abuse of personal data.

Safe and secure virtual worlds

Virtual worlds are built upon existing digital platforms, and thus replicate and often exacerbate their flaws, particularly regarding safety and security. Due to the all-encompassing nature of virtual worlds, concerns about data collection are heightened. The metaverse tracks unique habits, preferences, and activities, while VR hardware collects sensitive biomechanical data, proven by recent studies to identify individuals at rates similar to biometric data.⁵ It is not clear how companies will store that data, who will have access to it, and whether explicit consent will be obtained from users about its collection, indicating potential violations of data subject rights. These new technologies bring new cybersecurity risks, giving hackers the potential to manipulate entire virtual environments and social interactions to mislead users and trick them into acting in their interests. In a world where daily actions increasingly take place in a shared digital environment, users are exposed to new risks; for example, hackers could potentially record private online activities for blackmail, track users' movements to map the physical space they live in, or gain access to stored financial information and large volumes of personal data.⁶ Identity theft could enable bad actors to impersonate victims across social and professional settings, which becomes especially problematic when XR is used in high-stakes work, such as surgery.

Trilateral Research has worked on cybersecurity and data protection in emerging technologies across multiple EU-funded projects. [DARLENE⁷](#) is an ongoing Horizon 2020 project developing AR wearables with machine learning capabilities. This tool is designed for use by law enforcement agencies, and triggers many of the same concerns about data collection and usage that arise in the context of virtual worlds. DARLENE is designed to acknowledge and mitigate the potential adverse impacts of the project's outputs directly and from the earliest stages; the project incorporates the principles of responsible research and innovation, value-sensitive design, and ethics- and privacy-by-design, as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant legislation. In practice, these steps lead to a focus on ethical and legal issues such as data minimisation and explicit consent, facilitate collaborative discussions about these topics between project partners, and have resulted in a systematic approach which prevents these

⁴ Singh, Priyansha. (2020, February 14). *Why interoperability and openness are critical in Metaverse*. Oodlestechnologies. Retrieved April 19, 2023, from <https://www.oodlestechnologies.com/blogs/why-interoperability-and-openness-are-critical-in-metaverse/>.

⁵ Nair, Vivek, et al. (2023, February 17). *Unique Identification of 50,000+ Virtual Reality Users from Head & Hand Motion Data*. arXiv. Retrieved April 21, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.08927>

⁶ *What are the security and privacy risks of VR and AR*. Kaspersky. Retrieved April 21, 2023, from <https://usa.kaspersky.com/resource-center/threats/security-and-privacy-risks-of-ar-and-vr>.

⁷ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 883297.

considerations from being undermined by time or market pressures. Regular ethical, legal, privacy, and data protection impact assessments (DPIAs) are conducted to ensure adherence to these goals, as well as holistic analyses of project work from ethical, legal, and societal perspectives. DARLENE reflects the level of proactive oversight required when developing XR technologies. To ensure compliance with cybersecurity, privacy, and data protection laws, oversight must be an ongoing responsibility which evolves alongside technology.

The European Commission (EC) should pursue actions which encourage privacy and data collection to be addressed directly and as early as possible by developers. The EC should evaluate measures to strengthen compliance with and enforcement of existing legislation, particularly the GDPR, and ensure that XR companies do not process the data collected without users' explicit consent.⁸ The EC should also consider classifying information collected by XR technologies as identifiable data, and implement proactive measures to address the use of manipulative techniques, such as dark patterns, in the design of virtual worlds. The EC should also continue to encourage the adoption of privacy-by-design from the earliest stages of projects. Finally, the EC should consider initiatives to streamline public and private sector cybersecurity approaches and prevent a fragmented response to the challenges of virtual worlds. For example, despite the EC's proposed framework for an authenticated European Digital Identity, private companies are introducing individual identification systems for their own products,⁹ which will continue the fragmented approach which undermines confidence in the cybersecurity of new platforms.

Respectful virtual worlds

The third objective of the European Commission's vision is to empower 'people to engage in a secure, confident and responsible manner so that they benefit from virtual worlds with respect to EU values, way of living and rules, while giving users the freedom to choose how and when to use their digital identity, data and assets.' The protection of EU fundamental rights and principles is at the heart of this objective. Virtual worlds and metaverses have the potential to both enhance and interfere with fundamental rights.¹⁰ The EU should consider the possible human rights impacts, especially privacy and data protection implications of virtual worlds, considering that VR devices are increasingly capable of collecting significant volumes and various types of data through XR technologies. Combined with Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled data processing capabilities, the human rights and privacy and data protection implications require careful consideration. One possible intervention to enhance data protection laws would be to broaden the scope of article 9 (1) of the GDPR on the processing of special categories of personal data, to include all types of biometric data processing, as opposed to limiting this to biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying an individual.

Furthermore, the consumption of harmful online content by users may be experienced differently in virtual worlds, as opposed to other digital means. The immersive and increasingly realistic nature of XR technologies may exacerbate the psychological and emotional impacts of harmful online content to users, particularly in the case of vulnerable groups such as children. The EU should consider effective means of regulating harmful online content, particularly in the context of virtual worlds and metaverses. In doing so, the EU should consider the roles and responsibilities of XR providers and strengthen and monitor compliance with existing and proposed EU legislation, including the Digital Services Act, the proposed AI act, and the Digital Markets Act. The EU could also promote user empowerment through self-reporting measures and consider the need for user and/or machine identity verification.

⁸ Valle, Sebastião Barros and Daniel Berrick. (2023, January 25). *Reality Check: How is the EU ensuring data protection in XR technologies?* The Digital Constitutionalists. Retrieved April 21, 2023, from <https://digi-con.org/reality-check-how-is-the-eu-ensuring-data-protection-in-xr-technologies/>

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ See the Horizon 2020 TechEthos project deliverable 4.1 on an analysis of international and EU laws on the governance of XR technologies: Santiago, N., Howkins, B., Vinders, J., Rodrigues, R., Warso, Z., Bernstein, M., Gonzalez, G., Porcari, A. (2022). TechEthos D4.1: *Analysis of international and EU law and policy*. TechEthos Project Deliverable. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/7650731>.

Further recommendations for enhancing EU legal frameworks for the governance of virtual worlds, metaverses and XR were developed by Trilateral Research on behalf of the Horizon 2020 [TECHETHOS](https://www.techethos.eu)¹¹ project. This policy brief can be found on: <https://www.techethos.eu/enhancing-eu-legal-frameworks-digital-extended-reality/>.

Conclusion

To summarise, we recommend that the EC:

- Regulates and monitors the emerging market of virtual worlds to achieve greater competitiveness and diverse innovation;
- Ensure greater diversification of the market of virtual worlds by addressing, with the aim of overcoming, the challenge of XR devices-dependency on big tech companies to create increased openness and diversity of virtual worlds;
- Creates an environment where virtual worlds address interoperability, transparency and accountability considerations;
- Promotes EU data subject rights defined in the GDPR to prevent mass personal data collection and storage without explicit consent and encourage the adoption of privacy-by-design approaches;
- Encourages streamlining of public and private sector data protection and cybersecurity initiatives to promote a unified response to security vulnerabilities in virtual worlds;
- Addresses the use of manipulative techniques such as dark patterns used by companies to meet GDPR requirements without meaningfully informing users of data usage or obtaining explicit consent;
- Promotes EU fundamental rights and encourages the adoption of ethics-by-design approaches;
- Considers broadening the scope of article 9 (1) of the GDPR to include other types of biometric data processing within the special category of personal data, which may be generated through XR technologies in virtual worlds and metaverses;
- Promotes user empowerment through self-reporting measures and evaluate the need for user and/or machine verification in virtual worlds and metaverses.

Requests for further information or clarifications can be emailed to Julie.vinders@trilateralresearch.com.

Sincerely,

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